

Analysis of tweets of Slovene corporate users

Darja Fišer

Dept. of Translation, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana
Dept. of Knowledge Technologies, Jožef Stefan Institute

Monika Kalin Golob

Chair of Journalism, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana

Ljubljana, 20 September 2018

Motivation

- Qualitative study by Kalin Golob et al. 2018
- type 1:
 - the language of tweets is neutral & standard, sentences are short and nearly always contain a hyperlink
 - the only marked element is the frequent usage of exclamation marks and all caps
 - *ISKRENA HVALA VSEM DAROVALCEM!*
- type 2:
 - tweets are written in spoken tone, directly address the reader
 - frequent use of phraseology, colloquialisms and interjections
 - frequent use of questions, combinations of question and exclamation marks
 - *Je tvoj predplačniški račun prazen?*
- language style carefully selected for the content
 - content: announcements -> formal and standard, social events, invitations and campaigns -> colloquial
 - target audience: general -> neutral style, specialized -> neutral/colloquial
 - author: public institutions -> neutral and standard, companies -> visibility, colloquial, non-standard
 - news, products, persons, institutions and companies typically presented in a positive way

- Janes-Tviti (Erjavec et al. 2018)
 - 11.3 million tweets
 - 10.200 users (private, corporate)
- Part 1
 - production & posting dynamics
- Part 2
 - new media elements
- Part 3
 - language & keywords

Results 1: Production

User type

Users	No. of users	No. of tweets
Corporate	2612 (26%)	2,112,910 (19%)
Private	7627 (74%)	9,223,736 (81%)
Total	10,248 (100%)	11,336,646 (100%)

User sex

Users	Corporate	Private
Unknown	1,730,258 (82%)	134,048 (1%)
Private	271,729 (13%)	6,136,470 (67%)
Female	110,923 (5%)	2,953,218 (32%)
Total	2,112,910 (100%)	9,223,736 (100%)

Results 1: Dynamics

User production

No. of users	Corporate	Private
> 10.000 tweets	29 (1%)	129 (2%)
10.000 – 1000 tweets	422 (16%)	1867 (24%)
1000 – 100 tweets	1640 (63%)	4055 (53%)
< 100 tweets	521 (20%)	1576 (21%)
Total	2612 (100%)	7627 (100%)

Posting dynamics

Tweet length

Results 2: Interactive elements

- Likes
 - 0 likes: 4/5 corporate vs. 2/3 private tweets
- Retweeted tweets
 - >1 retweet: 17% corporate vs. 8% private
- Less interpersonal communication, more information dissemination

Results 2: New media elements

Hashtag per tweet	
Corporate	0,44
Private	0,24
Emoji per tweet	
Corporate	0,61
Private	1,31
Hyperlink per tweet	
Corporate	0,94
Private	0,28
Mention per tweet	
Corporate	0,31
Private	1,00

Corporate	
Hashtag	Freq.
#plts	18,703
#slonews	18,247
#PLTS	9,620
#Ljubljana	5,724
#izvršba	5,167
#NKDomzale	4,437
#olimpija	4,176
#rokomet	4,143
#junaki	3,941
#skupajdovrha	3,864

Corporate	
Mention	Freq.
@YouTube	8,325
@Nova24TV	6,903
@Val202	3,992
@rtvslo	3,866
@kzs_si	3,736
@union_olimpija	3,616
@JJansaSDS	3,464
@radioPrvi	3,128
@vladaRS	2,764
@nkmaribor	2,758

Emoji	Freq.	User	Freq.	Rel. freq.
:)	114,602	_RecycleMan	530	12,711
;)	55,763	JennParisBags	188	11,522
:D	17,715	EtiVelikonja	160	10,410
<3	13,688	ApartmaNet	184	10,105
:-)	9,672	TRENDtrgovina	436	10,049
;-)	4,926	Pawla40	228	9,720
:))	4,680	iPlace_si	125	8,860
❤️	3,679	bozicluka	92	8,290
:P	3,558	matejgaber22	99	7,223
😊	3,436	Modniovitki	424	7,011

Results 3: Language

- Language:
 - almost exclusively in Slovene (93 %)
 - exceptions (English): embassies, ministry of foreign affairs, president of the country, government
- Sentiment:
 - ½ of all corporate tweets have positive sentiment
- Standardness:
 - predominantly standard (80%), very nonstandard extremely rare (3%)
 - standard abbreviations (d. o. o., min.), standard punctuation
 - exceptions (non-standard): stand-up comedians, radio show hosts, musicians
- Parts of speech:
 - nearly 2x more proper nouns and numerals than in private tweets
 - much more frequent also conjunctions, prepositions, adjectives and common nouns
 - much less frequent interjections, particles, pronouns and adverbs
- More formal style & informative and influential function of corporate tweets

Results 3: Keywords

- Sentiment:
 - negative tweets stand out the most (accidents, disasters)
 - positive tweets typical for corporate communication (congratulations, invitations)
 - neutral tweets the Five Ws
- Standardness:
 - standard for announcements and ads
 - nonstandard ads for a specific (younger) target audience
- Sex:
 - indicates topics and styles intended for male/female audience
 - female fashion, shopping, food, parenting
 - male real estate, sports, music

Conclusions

- Confirmed
 - standard language and formal style prevails in corporate tweets
 - nonstandard language and informal style is rare but deliberate to appeal to the target audience
 - highly 1-way communication, not interactive, just a new dissemination channel for announcements and positive presentation
- Rejected
 - corporate users do not avoid evaluative lexis (high-ranked evaluative adjectives, especially superlatives)
- Future work
 - more fine-grained corporate account types (eg. media, corporations, public institutions)
 - reception of corporate tweets which contain non-standard, interactive and new media elements
- Contribution of the paper
 - systematic and methodologically advanced showcase of the potential of corpus-based approaches in communication studies, media studies and other related disciplines in social sciences which study language use

#tenks 😊

darja.fiser@ff.uni-lj.si

monika.kalin-golob@fdv.uni-lj.si